

TABLE 2—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF SALICYLALDEHYDE AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF URANYL CHELATE WITH SALICYLALDEHYDE

% Dioxane	Temp. = 30°C Mole fraction	$\mu = 0.1M \text{ NaClO}_4$		Medium = 75% (v/v) dioxane-water			
		pK		$\log K_1$		$\log K_2$	
		Practical	Thermodynamic	Practical	Thermodynamic	Practical	Thermodynamic
10	0.0296	8.53	8.64	6.68	6.79	5.88	5.99
25	0.0650	8.84	9.01	8.60	7.40	7.35	6.52
40	0.1233	9.16	9.51	7.18	8.13	6.66	7.01
60	0.2410	9.77	10.66	8.35	9.24	7.33	8.22
75	0.3870	10.15	12.03	9.26	11.16	8.11	10.01

Accuracy 0.02 to 0.05.

Calculation of the radius of the ion :

The effective ionic radius of the ligand anion was obtained by the Born equation¹⁰. The plot of $\Delta pK(pK_{\text{mix}} - pK_{\text{water}})$ against $\frac{1}{D}$ was found to be linear. The effective ionic radius obtained from the slope of the linear plot was 0.82Å for salicylaldehyde. The value observed is of the same order in magnitude as that obtained by Ohtaki¹¹ for oxalate and ammonium ions. The very low magnitude of the ionic radius may be due to the fact that this value does not give the size of the whole organic molecule but that of charged site, i.e. hydroxyl oxygen in salicylaldehyde molecule.

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Studies of Formation Constants of Lanthanoid Complexes with N-Benzoylphenyl Hydroxylamine

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THE determination of the formation constant values for the rare earth complexes with organic ligands containing active oxygen atom have aroused interest because of the flexibility of the coordination number of the rare earth ions. In contrast, the nature of the lanthanide-hydroxamate bond interaction remained unexplored. In this paper, the formation constant values of five lanthanide ions with N-benzoylphenylhydroxylamine (N-BPHA), determined in dioxane-water medium (3 : 1 v/v), are reported.

The chemicals used were of either E. Merck, G. R., B.D.H. or AR grade. Doubly distilled water (CO₂ free) and purified dioxane¹ were used. The perchlorates of lanthanides used were prepared by digesting the corresponding oxides (99.9% pure, Johnson Matthey) with perchloric acid and removing the excess acid by repeated evaporation under an electrical heater. Finally the perchlorates were dissolved in water and made up to a definite volume. Lanthanide ions were determined by oxalate precipitation and their subsequent ignition to their respective oxides². Free perchloric acid present in the metal perchlorate solutions were determined by running a known volume of the solution through a column of Amberlite IR-120 (H⁺-form) and titrating the liberated acid with a standard sodium hydroxide solution.

N-Benzoylphenylhydroxylamine (N-BPHA) : The reagent was prepared by the method as described earlier³. Before use, the reagent was repeatedly

recrystallised. The purity of the reagent was verified by m.p. (121°) determination and matching of the IR spectra.

Procedure: The general procedure consisted in the titration under inert (nitrogen) atmosphere at $30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$ with standard sodium hydroxide solution [$4.197 \times 10^{-2} M$ in 3:1 (v/v) dioxane-water medium] of a 40 ml dioxane-water (3:1 v/v) solution having a metal ion concentration $\sim 2 \times 10^{-3} M$, a reagent concentration $\sim 2 \times 10^{-3} M$, and sodium perchlorate in sufficient amount to maintain the initial ionic strength 0.1M. The pH-measurements were made with a Cambridge pH-meter having compatible glass (Universal type) and calomel electrodes connected by salt bridge. The dissociation constant of N-BPHA was determined in a similar manner. The pH-meter was calibrated in a way described by Van Uitert and Hass⁴. The pH-meter reading (B) was converted to the stoichiometric hydrogen ion concentration ($[H^+]$) using the relation

$$B = -\log [H^+] - \log U$$

where U is a function of the solvent composition and the ionic strength.

Calculation: Preliminary studies using two different concentrations of a metal ion keeping the metal to ligand ratio same revealed that no polynuclear complex species are formed. Moreover previous studies established the absence of hydroxo complex species in solution⁵. In order to determine the first two formation constants (K_1 and K_2) it was assumed that when $1 > \bar{n} > 0$, the concentration of tris- and other higher complex species in solution were negligible.

Under such condition eq. (1)

$$\sum_{n=0}^N (\bar{n} - n) [A^-]^n \beta_n = 0 \quad \dots (1)$$

may be rearranged to the linear form (2)

$$\frac{\bar{n}}{(1-\bar{n})[A^-]} = \frac{(2-\bar{n})[A^-]}{(1-\bar{n})} K_1 K_2 + K_2 \quad \dots (2)$$

Thus a plot of $\frac{\bar{n}}{(1-\bar{n})[A^-]}$ against $\frac{(2-\bar{n})[A^-]}{(1-\bar{n})}$ in

the limiting condition $\bar{n} < 1$ will provide a straight line from which K_1 is obtained as the intercept and $K_1 K_2$ as the slope. Again assuming that at $2 > \bar{n} > 1$, the first three complex species coexist in solution but the concentration of the higher complex species are negligible. Eq. (1) then may be reduced to the

linear form (3)

$$\frac{(\bar{n}-1)}{(2-\bar{n})[A^-]} + \frac{\bar{n}}{(2-\bar{n})K_1[A^-]^2} = \frac{(3-\bar{n})[A^-]}{(2-\bar{n})} K_2 K_3 + K_2 \quad \dots (3)$$

K_1 having been already determined, the least squares fit gave K_2 and K_3 using the value of K_1 in eq. (3). The values presented in Table 1 represent the mean values of K_2 (both the plots for K_2 yielded values in reasonably good agreement).

The practical acid dissociation constant (pK_a) of NBPFA as determined by us came out to be 10.80. Tandon *et al*⁶ reported the thermodynamic dissociation constant of N-BPHA in 1:1 aqueous-dioxane at 25° and 35° as 11.04 and 10.95 respectively.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF LANTHANIDE-N-BENZYLPHENYL HYDROXYLAMINE

Metal ion	$1/r(\text{\AA}^{-1})$	Log K_1	Log K_2	Log K_3	Log β_3
La ³⁺	0.942	7.77	6.64	5.94	20.35
Pr ³⁺	0.987	8.10	7.49	6.60	22.19
Nd ³⁺	1.005	8.69	7.54	6.92	23.15
Sm ³⁺	1.037	9.38	8.16	7.18	24.72
Gd ³⁺	1.066	9.13	8.00	7.07	24.20

Table 1 shows the first three formation constant values of the five lanthanide ions. In general, for a given metal ion, $\log K_1 > \log K_2 > \log K_3$. However, the difference between any two consecutive constants is quite small, indicating that there is an almost equal tendency for all the complex species to coexist in solution. It is apparent from Table 1 that the log K_1 values gradually increases with increasing $1/r$ (in \AA^{-1}) but in the case of Gd³⁺-ion, it shows a decline. This is probably the change in aquo-ion structure and depression of class-b character in the heavier lanthanide ions which govern the sequence of formation constant values throughout the series^{7,8}. Another cause of this anomaly may be some steric factors in N-BPHA molecule discriminating Gd³⁺ ion.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Ru(III) and Os(VIII) with 2,4,5-Triamino-6-Pyrimidinol

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IN continuation of the studies reported earlier from this laboratory¹⁻³ the use of 2,4,5-triamino-6-pyrimidinol⁴ for the colorimetric determination of Ru(III) and Os(VIII) is reported in this study.

Results and Discussion

Ruthenium : The broad experimental procedure for this work is as reported earlier⁵. Heating a 0.1 molar potassium chloride solution of a mixture of ruthenium (0.8-3 μg Ru/ml; the optimum concentration range from a Ringbom plot) and 60 fold amounts of the reagent adjusted to a pH range of 4.0-5.0 for 20 min on a water bath gave a violet red coloured solution with λ_{max} at 570 nm useful for the determination of ruthenium at the specified range of concentration. The Sandell's sensitivity of the system is 0.0036 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. From 8 aliquots of standard solution containing 1.98 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Ru, the standard deviation is 0.0050.

In determination of 2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of ruthenium the tolerance of other ions (conc. in $\mu\text{g/ml}$) is found to be as follows: Br^- , ClO_4^- , BO_3^{3-} , PO_4^{3-} (1000); F^- , I^- , NO_3^- , EDTA (200); tartrate, citrate, (100); Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} (400); Mg^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} (100); Mn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Zn^{2+} (60); Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Pb^{2+} (30); Sn^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Rh^{3+} , Ir^{3+} , Pt^{4+} and Os^{8+} (10). The presence of NO_2^- , CNS^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, thiourea, Ag^+ , Cu^{2+} and Au^{3+} causes interferences.

Osmium : The reaction with osmium in the optimum pH range of 7.0-8.5 is found to be instantaneous and is complete with 30 fold concentration of the reagent. The optimum range

of concentration is found to be 1.4-6.6 $\mu\text{g Os/ml}$ for the spectrophotometric determination at a λ_{max} of 490-500 nm. The Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction is 0.007 $\mu\text{g Os cm}^{-2}$. The standard deviation is 0.003 for 8 aliquots of standard solutions containing 4.7 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Os.

In the determination of 4.7 μg of Os/ml the tolerance of other ions (conc. in $\mu\text{g/ml}$) is found to be as follows: F^- , Br^- , CH_3COO^- , BO_3^{3-} , PO_4^{3-} (1000); I^- , NO_3^- , EDTA (500); CNS^- , citrate (250); Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Pb^{2+} (50); Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} ; Ru^{3+} (25); Mg^{2+} (20); Ag^+ , Sn^{2+} , Rh^{3+} , Ir^{3+} and Au^{3+} (5). In case of Zn, Cd, Mg and Sn, the absorbance was noted after centrifuging off the precipitated species: Hg^{2+} (50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) can co-exist in presence of 500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of I^- . Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} (100) and Ni^{2+} (30) can be masked with EDTA and Co (30) with CNS^- . The presence of NO_2^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6^{2-}$, thiourea, Fe^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} causes serious interferences.

Of the substituted pyrimidines which have been developed for the spectrophotometric determination of ruthenium and osmium⁶⁻⁹, the present compound is the most sensitive but however is not of high selectivity. The solution of the reagent is not very stable and needs to be prepared fresh.

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